

CONTEMPORARY FACETS OF BUSINESS SUCCESSES AMONG LEADING COMPANIES, OPERATING IN BULGARIA

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(a scientific article)

Abstract:

The current article unveils and analyzes some important factors, influencing diversity in strategic decision-making approaches in local companies. Researcher's attention is oriented to survey important characteristics of the strategic moves, undertaken by leading companies in Bulgaria.

Keywords: corporate strategy, business strategy, business organizations, strategic management, crisis management.

JEL classification: L100, L190, L200, L210.

Full-text:

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